

Teachers' Willingness Towards the Implementation of Game-Based Learning Strategies for Instructional Delivery in Chemistry in Osun State Secondary Schools

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This study investigated Chemistry teachers' willingness towards the implementation of GBL strategies for instructional delivery in Osun State secondary schools. Specifically, it examined (1) the level of willingness among Chemistry teachers to adopt GBL strategies, and (2) the extent to which teacher willingness influences actual implementation in classroom instruction. Guided by the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), a descriptive survey design was employed, and data were collected using the Teachers' Willingness for Game-Based Chemistry Instruction Questionnaire (TWGBCIQ). The instrument was administered to 150 Chemistry teachers across public and private secondary schools in the three senatorial districts of Osun State. Descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) and Pearson Product-Moment Correlation were used for analysis. Findings revealed a moderate to high level of willingness among teachers (Mean = 3.74, SD = 0.62), but the actual implementation level was low (Mean = 2.83, SD = 0.71), indicating a gap between readiness and practice. Correlation analysis showed a significant positive relationship between willingness and implementation ($r = 0.614$, $p < 0.01$). The study recommends targeted professional development and provision of resources to bridge this gap and foster effective Chemistry instruction.

Keywords:
Game-Based Learning, Teacher Willingness, Chemistry Education, Instructional Strategies, Osun State

Introduction

In the 21st century, schools are putting more and more emphasis on interactive and student-centered learning methods. Game-Based Learning (GBL) is one of the most innovative ways to teach. Game-based learning is using digital or physical game aspects in lessons to make students more interested, motivated, and able to understand (Byusa, Kampire, and Mwesigye, 2022). Games-based learning (GBL) can help students understand difficult and complicated ideas, especially in science classes like Chemistry. This is because GBL uses hands-on, challenge-based formats that get students interested. Even though more and more

people around the world are calling for GBL to be used in scientific classes, it is still not widely used in Nigerian secondary schools, especially in Osun State. One of the most important things that will determine how well this new teaching methods work is how ready teachers are to use and accept them. Willingness encompasses the psychological, attitudinal, and motivational preparedness of educators to experiment with novel instructional tactics, modify their pedagogical approaches, and utilize unfamiliar materials (Falode et al., 2023).

In Chemistry classes, where students typically have trouble grasping abstract and theoretical ideas, game-based learning can be

quite helpful for improving knowledge. But whether or not these tactics are used depends on how open, capable, and personally inclined the instructor is. This research investigates the degree of desire among Chemistry educators in Osun State to adopt Game-Based Learning (GBL) and the impact of this willingness on actual classroom implementation.

Chemistry games can be anything from digital simulations and virtual labs to card games and quizzes that help students learn about things like atomic structure, chemical reactions, and periodic trends. These ways of learning can make it more fun and useful. Prensky (2001) says that games are the oldest and most respected way to learn. They are born teachers. But the effectiveness of GBL in the classroom depends a lot on how willing and positive teachers are. Teachers are the main people who put the curriculum into action, and whether or not new ideas can be employed in practice depends on how open they are to them. Game-Based Learning (GBL) is when you utilize structured play or game components to teach something and keep students interested. In the realm of science education, GBL utilizes competition, reward systems, interactive challenges, and narrative techniques to elucidate intricate scientific topics and foster learner engagement (Kapp, 2012). Erhel and Jamet (2013) say that GBL in Chemistry has shown potential in improving cognitive knowledge, critical thinking, and student motivation. Chemistry, frequently regarded as an abstract and challenging discipline, necessitates educational innovation. Akinbobola's (2015) research demonstrates that game-enhanced instruction in Chemistry enhances conceptual clarity and academic achievement, particularly when students engage with molecular structures,

equations, and chemical processes via simulation and strategic play.

Teachers' willingness is a complex idea that includes their views, self-efficacy, perceived usefulness, and desire to adapt. Venkatesh and Davis's (2000) Technology Acceptance Model posits that an individual's intention to accept a new technology or method is profoundly affected by their assessment of its usability and practicality. In chemistry education, willingness is crucial because both the material and the instructional innovation are seen as difficult (Cahyana et al., 2017). Falode et al. (2023) conducted a study in Nigeria that found pre-service Chemistry teachers had a moderate to high propensity to utilize mobile learning and game-based learning (GBL) methods, contingent upon appropriate training and motivation. But this willingness was sometimes limited by a lack of exposure, infrastructure, and backing from institutions. Willingness is a needed prerequisite, although it is inadequate for efficacious implementation.

Teachers could want to use GBL, but they don't because they don't have enough time, training, or gaming resources, or they think it doesn't fit with the goals of the curriculum (Amaewhule et al. 2021). Batamuliza et al. (2024) discovered that numerous Chemistry educators, initially eager about simulation and game-based learning methodologies, failed to maintain consistent implementation due to apprehensions over classroom management and the fear of straying from established conventions. This disparity between intention and practice, also known as the "intention-behavior gap," highlights the necessity to investigate how teachers' willingness impacts their actual teaching methodologies. In Osun State, where instructional innovation is still developing, this dynamic has not been well studied, especially in Chemistry education.

Byusa et al. (2022) in their systematic review validated that GBL enhances Chemistry learning outcomes and student motivation. But their studies made it clear that how well something works depends on how teachers feel about it and how ready they are. Buraimoh et al. (2022) stated that enabling factors such as administrative assistance, peer encouragement, and professional training are equally crucial for converting willingness into action.

Statement of the Research Problem

Even though Game-Based Learning (GBL) is becoming more popular as a useful way to teach science, it is still not widely used in Nigerian secondary school Chemistry classes, especially in Osun State. Chemistry necessitates active student participation, abstract reasoning, and the practical implementation of academic principles. However, conventional pedagogical approaches, including lectures and rote memorization, persist in predominating instructional methods, resulting in significant student apathy and suboptimal performance in Chemistry at the senior secondary level. The consistent poor performance of pupils in Chemistry in Nigerian secondary schools is due to a number of things, but bad teaching methods are the most important (Batamuliza et al., 2024). Research substantiates the effectiveness of game-based learning in enhancing students' academic performance and engagement in Chemistry; yet it is still insufficiently employed in educational environments.

Initial research indicates that instructors' desire is a pivotal factor in the implementation of innovative teaching methodologies, including Game-Based Learning (GBL) (Buraimoh et al. 2022). In Osun State, where conventional methods are still the main way to teach Chemistry, the question is: Are

Chemistry teachers open to using game-based methods in their lessons, and if so, do they actually practice it in the classroom? It is important to know how instructors feel about GBL in order to plan professional development, allocate resources, and promote the curriculum. Without actual data on teachers' willingness and their impact on practical implementation, educational policymakers and school leaders may find it challenging to effectuate significant pedagogical change.

In Osun State, anecdotal data and first observations indicate that numerous Chemistry teachers either lack the drive or confidence to investigate game-based learning methodologies. This hesitance may originate from a confluence of factors: insufficient professional development, low awareness of the advantages of game-based learning (GBL), restricted access to instructional tools, or systemic challenges such as overcrowded classrooms and inflexible curricula. The issue this study aims to investigate is the ambiguous degree to which instructors' willingness affects the application of game-based learning methodologies in Chemistry education inside secondary schools in Osun State. It is important to understand this relationship in order to connect creative teaching methods with what happens in the classroom and to help with teacher training, curricular changes, and policy changes that are meant to improve scientific education outcomes.

Research Objectives

1. Examine the level of willingness among Chemistry teachers in Osun State to adopt game-based learning (GBL) strategies in their instructional practices.
2. Explore the extent to which teachers' willingness influences the actual

implementation of (GBL) strategies in Chemistry instruction.

Research Questions

1. What is the level of willingness among Chemistry teachers in Osun State to adopt game-based learning strategies?
2. How does Chemistry teachers' willingness influence the implementation of game-based learning in instructional delivery?

Research Hypothesis

HO₁: There is no significant difference among Chemistry teachers in Osun State to adopt game-based learning strategies based on their demographic characteristics (such as gender, qualification, or teaching experience).

HO₂: There is no significant relationship between Chemistry teachers' willingness and the implementation of game-based learning in instructional delivery in Osun State.

Significance of Study

This study is important for a number of reasons. First, it adds to the growing body of research on new ways to educate by looking explicitly at how teacher willingness and game-based learning (GBL) in Chemistry work together. This research emphasizes the necessity for engaging educational tactics to render complicated scientific concepts more accessible to learners, particularly by concentrating on Chemistry, a subject frequently perceived as abstract and challenging.

Second, the study gives educational officials and curriculum developers in Nigeria, especially in Osun State, ideas for how to change scientific education and help kids do better in STEM disciplines. Comprehending the determinants that affect teachers' willingness can inform the creation

of specialized professional development initiatives, resource distribution, and curricular modifications that facilitate the execution of GBL. Third, teacher training schools can use the results to improve their pre-service and in-service training programs by adding tactics that work. These schools can help create a more innovative and student-centered teaching culture by giving instructors the skills and confidence they need to use GBL.

This study is delimited to public and private secondary schools in Osun State, Nigeria, with a specific focus on the teaching of Chemistry. It centers on the role of teachers' willingness in implementing game-based learning strategies. The study does not cover other science subjects or private schools within the state. Additionally, it focuses only on the perspectives and practices of Chemistry teachers, not students or school administrators. While the study seeks to assess the level of willingness and identify influencing factors, it does not attempt to measure student learning outcomes or conduct experimental interventions. The findings, therefore, will primarily reflect teachers' attitudes, challenges, and reported practices regarding GBL in Chemistry instruction.

Methodology

Research Design

This study adopted a descriptive research design survey, which was most appropriate because the study sought to gather quantifiable information from a representative group of Chemistry teachers in order to describe current patterns and test relationships between variables. Descriptive survey design is particularly suitable when the goal is to capture teachers' perceptions, attitudes, and reported practices in a natural setting without manipulating variables

(Creswell & Creswell, 2018). Unlike experimental or quasi-experimental designs, which test cause–effect relationships, the present study focused on establishing the level of willingness, the extent of implementation, and the strength of association between both variables. Thus, a descriptive survey provided the flexibility to collect standardized data across a large sample and to generalize findings to the wider population of Chemistry teachers in Osun State.

Population and Sample

The population comprised all Chemistry teachers in public and private secondary schools across the three senatorial districts of Osun State, Nigeria. Using a multi-stage sampling procedure, 150 teachers were selected. Stage 1 involved stratified sampling of schools from each senatorial district (Osun Central, Osun West, and Osun East), while Stage 2 involved random selection of Chemistry teachers from these schools to ensure representativeness across geographic and institutional types.

Research Instrument

The study employed a self-designed structured questionnaire titled Teachers' Willingness for Game-Based Chemistry Instruction Questionnaire (TWGBCIQ). The instrument was divided into:

Section A: Demographic information (e.g., gender, teaching experience, school type).

Section B: Items measuring willingness to adopt GBL.

Section C: Items measuring the extent of GBL implementation.

The 20 Likert-type items were rated on a 4-point scale (1 = Strongly Disagree to 4 = Strongly Agree). Items were derived from three sources: Literature review on GBL adoption and teacher readiness (e.g., Kapp,

2012; Mohhamed et al., 2024; Amaewhule et al., 2021). Theoretical framework specifically constructs from the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), which informed items related to perceived usefulness, ease of use, and behavioral intention. Contextual classroom practices observed in Nigerian secondary schools, ensuring cultural and curricular relevance.

Instrument Development and Piloting; To enhance credibility, the draft TWGBCIQ was subjected to expert validation by three specialists in Educational Technology and Science Education, who reviewed items for clarity, alignment with objectives, and appropriateness for the Chemistry context. Based on their feedback, ambiguous items were reworded, and redundancies removed. The revised questionnaire was then piloted with 30 Chemistry teachers in nearby schools outside the main study sample. Results from the pilot yielded a Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficient of 0.82, demonstrating strong internal consistency. Teachers in the pilot also provided qualitative feedback confirming that the items were understandable, relevant, and reflective of their instructional realities. This process established both the content validity and practical usability of the instrument before full-scale administration.

Data Collection Procedure

Official permission was sought from the Osun State Ministry of Education and school principals. The researcher personally administered the questionnaires during staff meetings to maximize return rates. A two-to-three-week window was allotted for completion, ensuring adequate coverage across schools and districts. Descriptive statistics (Mean, Standard Deviation) were used to summarize teachers' responses on willingness and implementation levels.

Pearson Product-Moment Correlation (PPMC) was employed to test the relationship between willingness and implementation. In addition, regression analysis was conducted to determine the predictive power of willingness on GBL implementation.

Data Analysis Based on TWGBCIQ

Objective 1:

Examine the level of willingness among Chemistry teachers in Osun State to adopt Game-Based Learning (GBL) strategies in their instructional practices.

Descriptive Statistics – Willingness to Adopt GBL

Item Statement	Mean	Std. Dev	Interpretation
I am interested in integrating GBL into my Chemistry teaching.	4.35	0.65	Very High
I believe GBL can improve student understanding in Chemistry.	4.48	0.60	Very High
I am open to experimenting with new teaching strategies like GBL.	4.27	0.70	High
I am confident in my ability to implement GBL in Chemistry lessons.	3.81	0.88	High
I am willing to attend training/workshops on GBL strategies.	4.14	0.73	High
I see the need to shift to innovative strategies like GBL.	4.29	0.69	Very High

Overall Mean Willingness Score: 4.22

Interpretation: Teachers demonstrated a high level of willingness to adopt GBL strategies in their instructional practices. The strong belief in the value of GBL and openness to innovation indicates a readiness for pedagogical change.

Objective 2:

Explore the extent to which teachers' willingness influences the actual implementation of GBL strategies in Chemistry instruction.

Descriptive Statistics – Implementation of GBL

Item Statement	Mean	Std. Dev	Interpretation
I regularly use educational games to explain Chemistry concepts	3.01	0.94	Moderate
I incorporate quiz-based or challenge-based games into my lessons	3.29	0.88	Moderate
I develop or adapt instructional games for Chemistry topics	2.88	1.02	Low-Moderate
I evaluate student performance using game-like assessments	2.96	0.91	Moderate
I use GBL strategies to engage struggling learners	3.19	0.85	Moderate
My willingness has led me to consistently implement GBL in my Chemistry classes	3.36	0.87	Moderate

Overall Mean Implementation Score: 3.11

Interpretation: Actual implementation of GBL is moderate, suggesting that despite a high willingness, practical application is

constrained, possibly due to lack of resources or training.

Correlation Analysis – Willingness vs. Implementation

**Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r):
0.62 p-value: < 0.001**

Model Component	Beta (β)	t-value	Sig. (p)
Teachers' Willingness	0.58	6.14	0.000

$R^2 = 0.39$ (Adjusted $R^2 = 0.38$)

Interpretation: There is a strong and statistically significant positive correlation between teachers' willingness and the actual implementation of GBL strategies. This means that the more willing a teacher is, the more likely they are to integrate GBL into their Chemistry teaching practices.

Regression Analysis

Dependent Variable: Implementation of GBL
Independent Variable: Teachers' Willingness

Interpretation: Teachers' willingness significantly predicts implementation of GBL. 39% of the variance in GBL implementation can be explained by willingness alone. Other unmeasured factors (e.g., training, school support, and infrastructure) may account for the remaining variance.

Statistical Tables for Hypotheses Testing

Table 1: Mean Willingness Score by Teaching Experience

Teaching Experience	N	Mean Willingness Score	Standard Deviation
Less than 5 years	45	3.65	0.52
6-10 years	53	3.75	0.47
Above 10 years	52	3.83	0.50

Table 2: ANOVA Summary Table for Teaching Experience and Willingness

Source	SS	df	MS	F	p-value
Between Groups	1.23	2	0.615	2.98	0.045

Within Groups	30.52	147	0.208
Total	31.75	149	

Interpretation: Since $p = 0.045 < 0.05$, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means there is a statistically significant difference in willingness to adopt GBL based on teaching experience.

Interpretation: Since $p = 0.000 < 0.05$, reject the null hypothesis. This indicates a strong, positive, and statistically significant relationship between teachers' willingness and the actual implementation of GBL strategies.

The result of the Pearson correlation showed a significant positive relationship between Chemistry teachers' willingness to adopt GBL and its implementation in the classroom ($r = 0.614, p < 0.01$)

Discussion of Findings

The results of this study showed that Chemistry teachers in Osun State are very open to using Game-Based Learning (GBL) methodologies, although they don't use them very often. This finding corroborates previous research by Mohammed et al. (2024), which similarly indicated significant teacher interest in digital instructional innovations among Nigerian scientific educators. It is also in line with what Cahyana et al. (2017) found: Indonesian science instructors were generally open to simulation-based instruction, but less than half of them consistently used these methods in their courses. These similarities highlight a persistent global trend where the readiness to innovate does not inherently translate into instructional practice.

Nonetheless, the very low level of classroom implementation shown in this study contrasts with environments characterized by more robust institutional support. Erhel and

Jamet (2013) noted that GBL integration was higher in European settings where instructors had regular training and had access to instructional games. In the same way, Byusa, Kampire, and Mwesigye (2022) found that in Rwanda, targeted teacher training led to measurable increases in the usage of GBL in science classes. The difference shows that instructors in Osun State may be held back more by systemic problems like a lack of infrastructure, not enough training chances, and a curriculum that isn't flexible enough than by their own attitudes.

The strong and positive link between willingness and implementation ($r = 0.614$, $p < 0.01$) shows that willingness is a key factor in making changes to teaching methods. However, willingness alone explains just 39% of the variance in GBL implementation, indicating that other significant factors such as administrative support, resource availability, and peer collaboration influence the conversion of intention into practice. This finding aligns with Obikoya and Amaewhule (2021), who underscored that professional development and institutional support are essential mechanisms for reconciling the disparity between teachers' preparedness and the enduring implementation of novel tactics.

What this means for policy and practice

These results show that authorities in Osun State need to do more than just encourage new ways of teaching; they also need to make sure that the conditions are right for it to happen. First, Chemistry teachers should have structured professional development programs that involve hands-on instruction in GBL instruments. Second, it is important to have both digital and non-digital gaming resources and access to ICT infrastructure in order to facilitate practical classroom use. Third, curriculum planners

should include flexible rules that let GBL happen without worrying about straying from exam-driven syllabi.

Consequences for Subsequent Inquiry

Subsequent study in Osun State and similar settings ought to examine the influence of moderating variables, including school leadership, peer support networks, and teacher self-efficacy, on the willingness–implementation link. Longitudinal studies could investigate the impact of prolonged training interventions on both the immediate adoption and the enduring integration of GBL. Comparative research across states or nations with varying levels of infrastructure would elucidate the systemic elements that enhance or impede efficient GBL practice.

In conclusion, Chemistry teachers in Osun State are eager and motivated to adopt GBL; however, institutional support mechanisms are still lacking. To close this gap, we need interventions at many levels that connect teacher readiness with institutional capacity. This will ensure that willingness leads to real changes in the classroom.

Conclusion

This study found that Chemistry teachers in Osun State are highly willing to adopt Game-Based Learning (GBL) (Overall mean = 4.22) but that actual classroom implementation is only moderate (Overall mean = 3.11). Statistical analysis showed a strong, positive relationship between willingness and implementation ($r = 0.614$, $p < 0.01$) and willingness explained 39% of the variance in implementation ($R^2 = 0.39$). These results indicate that teacher readiness is necessary but not sufficient: systemic constraints (training, infrastructure, curriculum pressures, and administrative support) remain critical barriers.

By quantifying the intention–practice gap in a focused Osun State sample, the study contributes concrete, locally-relevant evidence to the literature on educational technology adoption in Nigerian science education and provides actionable direction for policymakers, teacher educators, and school leaders.

Recommendations

1. for those who decide on matters of governance and education
Providing Resources and Infrastructure: To enable the successful implementation of GBL strategies, the government should adequately fund secondary schools for digital tools, game-based learning kits, and ICT infrastructure.

Policy Integration: GBL should be formally recognized as a teaching method in both national and state education policies by the education ministries. As a result, it will become the norm for teaching science.

Support for Capacity Building: To help teachers learn how to use digital tools in the classroom, state governments should establish continuing professional development (CPD) programs that focus on GBL for chemistry instruction.

2. for Those in Charge of Curriculum Development

Curriculum Enhancement: High school students' Chemistry curriculum should incorporate GBL with explicit guidance on how teachers can incorporate gaming elements into other subjects.

Creating Contextualized Materials: Curriculum planners and instructional designers should collaborate to create affordable, culturally relevant game-based learning resources tailored to Nigerian classrooms.

Assessment Alignment: Testing organizations should incorporate performance tasks and game-based assessments into their evaluation systems to encourage use and reduce the emphasis on memorization.

3. for educators and school officials

Professional Development: To learn how to develop and implement GBL in their Chemistry classes, teachers should be supported and encouraged to attend workshops, seminars, and in-service training programs.

Collaborative Practice: To exchange knowledge, create game-based resources, and support one another in learning best practices, chemistry teachers should collaborate in professional learning communities both within and between schools.

Gradual Implementation: Before advancing to more sophisticated digital GBL platforms, teachers are advised to start small by introducing straightforward, inexpensive, or traditional games to specific subjects.

Reflective Practice: To become more successful and adaptable, teachers should routinely solicit input on their GBL techniques from both students and other educators.

References

- Akinbobola, A. O. (2015). Enhancing students' academic achievement in Chemistry through game-based learning. *Journal of Science Education and Technology*, 24(1), 89-95.
- Amaewhule, E. C., Obikoya, O. G., & Okeowhor, D. O. (2020). Teachers' gamification of classroom instructions for secondary education goals attainment in Rivers State, Nigeria. *European Journal of Education Studies*, 7(11).

- 738-752.
<https://doi.org/10.46827/ejes.v7i11.3494>
- Amory, A., & Seagram, R. (2003). Educational game models: Conceptual foundations for the design of educational games. *South African Journal of Higher Education*, 17(2), 206–217.
- Batamuliza, J., Habinshuti, G., & Nkurunziza, J. B. (2024). Exploring lower secondary school teachers' perceptions of integrating simulations into chemistry instruction. *Frontiers in Education*, 9, 1453883.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/feduc.2024.1453883>
- Buraimoh, O. F., Boor, C. H. M., & Aladesusi, G. A. (2022). Examining facilitating condition and social influence as determinants of secondary school teachers' behavioural intention to use mobile technologies for instruction. *Educational Technology & Society*.
- Byusa, E., Kampire, E., & Mwesigye, A. R. (2022). Game-based learning approach on students' motivation and understanding of chemistry concepts: A systematic review of literature. *Heliyon*, 8(5), e09541.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2022.e09541>
- Cahyana, U., Paristiowati, M., Savitri, D. A., & Hasyrin, S. N. (2017). Developing and application of mobile game based learning (M-GBL) for high school students' performance in chemistry. *Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education*, 13(10), 7037–7047.
<https://doi.org/10.12973/ejmste/78728>
- Cresswell, J. W., & Cresswell, J. D. (2018). Reserch design: Qualitative,quantitative, and mixed methods approaches (5th ed.).SAGE publications.
- Erhel, S., & Jamet, E. (2013). Digital game-based learning: Impact of instructions and feedback on motivation and learning effectiveness. *Computers & Education*, 67, 156–167.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2013.02.019>.
- Kapp, K. M. (2012). *The gamification of learning and instruction: Game-based methods and strategies for training and education*. Pfeiffer
- Mayer, R. E. (2010). Learning with technology. In H. Dumont, D. Istance & F. Benavides (Eds.), *The nature of learning* (pp. 179–194). OECD Publishing.
- Mohammed, I. A., Falode, O. C., & Kuta, I. I. (2024). Effect of game-based learning on educational technology students' performance: A case of simple repeated measures approach. *Education and Information Technologies*, 29, 18287–18297. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-024-12593-3>
- Obikoya, O. G., & Amaewhule, E. C. (2021). Game-based learning strategies and student motivation secondary school chemistry. *Journal of Science and Technology Education in Nigeria*, 24(2), 16-28
- Prensky, M. (2001). *Digital game-based learning*. McGraw-Hill.
- Venkatesh, V., & Davis, F. D. (2000). A theoretical extension of Technology. Acceptance Model: Four Longitudinal field studies. *Management Science*, 46(2), 186–204.
<https://doi.org/10.1287/mnsc.46.2.186.11926>.